

INFLUENCE OF ADDITIVES ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH-MODULUS ASPHALT CONCRETE

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Abstract

The appearance of premature cracks in freeway chase bodies is a worrying problem that requires in-depth analysis and remedial action. By identifying potential causes and proposing targeted recommendations, this study aims to help the responsible authorities make informed decisions to prevent such problems in the future and ensure the durability of road infrastructure. Premature cracking and rutting are common problems in pavements that can compromise their durability and safety. The use of specific additives in asphalt concrete can help prevent these deficiencies. The use of ZQ1 additive alone can lead to premature cracking in pavements, while PR FLEX 20 additive can increase the risk of rutting. However, a judicious combination of the two additives, with specific percentages of 2% for ZQ1 and 5% for PR FLEX 20, can prevent these shortcomings, improve pavement durability and optimize the mechanical properties of high-modulus asphalt concrete (BBME). In addition, this approach offers a promising solution for improving pavement durability and performance over time, opening the door to further studies to optimize the use of this additive combination in field applications.

Keywords: Road, Additives, Cracking, Asphalt Concrete, Durability, Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Road networks are one of the most important elements in a country's economic development. They facilitate economic and commercial exchanges between populations, and the movement of people and their goods. However, many Algerian roads are in poor condition, a situation attributable to a number of factors (increasing traffic and loads, climatic conditions, use of materials, lack of maintenance, etc.). In this article, the influence of additives on asphalt concrete cracking is studied, using as a real-life example the treatment of a pavement problem on the 32 km section of the east-oust freeway crossing the wilaya of Relizane between the boundary with the wilaya of Chlef and Hemadna.

Many researchers have worked on additives, such as Padhan et al (2013), who carried out an environmentally friendly approach to the disposal of environmentally hazardous materials, while Ahmedzade et al (2015) addressed the effects of residual polypropylene additive on bituminous binder properties.

For the influence of temperature on bituminous concretes, Perez-lepe et al (2007) carried out a rheological evaluation of the High-Temperature Stability of different polymer-modified bitumens; on the other hand, Ragni et al (2018) studied the effect of temperature and chemical additives on short-term aging.

Currently, Radziszewski et al (2023) have evaluated the aging of polymer-modified bitumen foam with the Bio-Flux additive and Gómez et al (2021) have introduced a new isocyanate-based additive to improve asphalt performance.

2. PROBLEMATIC

Following the opening of section W1 (a 32 km stretch of the east-west freeway crossing the wilaya of Relizane between the border with the wilaya of Chlef and Hemadna) in 2009, the control and monitoring office for this section noted the appearance of micro-cracks in 2011, which began to progress to the state of macro-cracks (named problem P1) requiring light maintenance of the thin type A asphalt concrete wearing course (BBMA) and the high-modulus asphalt concrete binder course (BBME) in 2015, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Premature cracking of wearing course in 2011

The pavement body remained stable for three years (from 2015 to 2018) before the appearance of a few rutting points (named problem P2). The development of the crack is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Fissure in Advanced Condition in 2020

Data collection was carried out by analyzing inspection reports, topographical surveys and meteorological data to understand the environmental conditions and characteristics of the pavement.

Secondly, a materials evaluation based on an analysis of the properties of the materials used in the construction of the pavement, notably high modulus asphalt concrete (BBME) and any additives used, such as ZQ1 and PR FLEX20.

Also, visual examinations through detailed crack inspections to determine their extent, shape and location.

The aim of these actions is to achieve the following:

- Crack identification: Classification of cracks according to their shape (transverse, longitudinal, cross-shaped, etc.) and location on the pavement.
- Potential causes of premature cracking: Analysis of factors that could contribute to the appearance of these cracks, such as traffic loads, temperature variations, construction defects, material quality and environmental conditions.
- Impact of environmental conditions: Assessment of the effect of climatic conditions, such as freeze-thaw cycles, humidity, precipitation and UV exposure, on the development of premature cracks.

This investigation aims to solve two problems P1(macro crack) and P2 (rutting) based on the approach between the following 3 actions:

- Action N°01: The formulations adopted to produce the BBME.
- Action N°02: The relationship between temperature and the two problems P1 and P2.
- Action N°03: Test results to determine the cause of the problems.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The formulations adopted for the binder course are high-modulus asphalt concrete (HMAB). Two formulation studies were carried out, the first in 2008 and the second in 2014, the results of which are summarized in TABLE 1.

After analyzing the tables, it was found that the bituminous mix in the 02 formulas is made up of 0/2 sand and 2/6.3 and 6.3/10 gravel representing the mineralogical body on the one hand, and 40/50 bitumen plus an additive representing the hydrocarbon binder on the other.

Concerning the mineral body, the same proportions were adopted in the 2 formulas except for the change of origin which differentiates them, but the review of documents shows that the mechanical performances of aggregates from the Ain Defla or Mascara quarries are identical and acceptable, so this approach excludes the probability of non-Conformity of the mineral body for the creation of the two problems P1 or P2.

Table 1: Formulation of Materials in 2008 and 2014

BBME formula in 2008		BBME formula in 2014	
Sand 0/2 Froha-Mascara	34 %	Sand 0/2 Ain Defla	34 %
Gravel 2/6.3 Froha-Mascara	25 %	Gravel 2/6.3 Ain Defla	23 %
Gravel 6.3/10 Froha-Mascara	41 %	Gravel 6.3/10 Ain Defla	43 %
Bitumen 35/50 Naftal	5.7 PPC	Bitumen 40/50 REPSOL	5.5 PPC
Additive ZQ 1	0.55 PPC	Additive PR FLEX 20	0.4 PPC

With regard to the change in hydrocarbon binder, and going back to TABLE 1, it is clear that the bitumen class is 35/50 in the 2 formulations, and consequently this class can in no way be the cause of the two problems. On the other hand, the change in additive in the 02 formulations may be the likely source of the cracking (P1) and rutting (P2) problems.

For the second action and to understand the behavior of each additive (AD) with respect to the thermal change (ΔT) and the phenomenon (PH) accompanied through the experiment obtained and documents available.

Fig. 3 below illustrates the results obtained to explain the relationship between AD, ΔT and PH:

Figure 3: Influence of Temperature Variation on Additives

Fig. 3 gives an overview of binder consistency as a function of service temperature. Experience has shown that ZQ-1 provides very good consistency at high temperatures and poor resistance to cracking at low temperatures, whereas PR FLEX 20 provides very good consistency at low temperatures and poor resistance to rutting at high temperatures.

A series of demonstration tests were carried out to validate this theory.

Tests on the BBME layer studied were carried out in accordance with standard NF EN 14023 (Delorme, 2007). The tests frequently used in Algeria are needle penetrability NF EN 1426 (Sarroukh, 2021) and softening point by the Ball and Ring method NF EN 1427 (Airey, 2009).

The results of tests carried out on pure bitumen with the additive ZQ1 are summarized in TABLE 2, and those carried out on pure bitumen with the additive PR Flex in TABLE 3. For each case, three samples were prepared and analyzed.

Table 2: Test results for pure bitumen + ZQ1 additive

N°	BP weight in g	Pure bitumen class	Weight of ZQ1 in g	ZQ1/Bitumen ratio in %	BP + Additive softening point TBA (° C)	Needle penetrability	BP +Additive class
1	140	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	13.496	9.64	100	15.5	10-40 Class 2 according to NF EN 14023
						23.6	
						17.6	
2	74	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	5.729	8	100	27.6	25-55 Class 3 according to NF EN 14023
						31.7	
						27.9	
3	84	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	4.200	5	61	23.9	10-40 Class 2 according to NF EN 14023
						17.7	
						17.8	

Table 3: Test Results for pure bitumen + PR Flex additive

N°	BP weight in g	Pure bitumen class	Weight of PR Flex in g	PR Flex /Bitumen ratio in %	BP + Additive softening point TBA (° C)	Needle penetrability	BP +Additive class
1	130.6	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	6.53	5	53	37	25-55 class 3 according to NF EN 14023
						23.6	
						34	
2	157.7	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	12.616	8	55	35	25-55 class 3 according to NF EN 14023
						31.7	
						35	
3	169		16.9	10	57	3	25-55 class 3
						17.7	

		40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)				17.8	according to NF EN 14023
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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By grouping all the results illustrated in TABLE 2, we can say that ZQ-1 modified bitumen is class 2 (NF EN 14023) with a penetrability of 10/40 (hard) and a softening temperature above 80°C. Analysis of these results shows that use of the ZQ1 additive alone can cause premature cracking in BBME samples.

On the other hand, and by grouping all the results illustrated in TABLE 3, we can say that the bitumen modified by PR FLEX 20 is class 25/55 with a softening temperature below 55°C (very flexible), hence the Analysis of these results show that the use of the additive PR FLEX 20 alone can lead to an increased risk of rutting in BBME samples.

It is therefore necessary to identify the specific percentages of ZQ1 and PR FLEX 20 additives that will prevent both premature cracking and rutting in BBME samples.

To achieve this goal, confirmation tests were carried out using several formulas to remedy this instability, and the results obtained are summarized in TABLE 4:

Table 4: Tests carried out on BBME Samples with ZQ1 Additive and PR FLEX 20

N°	Tare weight in g	Total weight in g	weight of pure bitumen in g	Pure bitumen class	Weight of ZQ1 in g	ZQ1/Bitumen ratio in %	Weight of PR Flex in g	PR Flex /Bitumen ratio in %	BP+Additive Softening TBA(°C)	Needle penetrability	BP +Additive class
1	91.42	375.92	284.5	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	9.95	3.5	9.95	3.5	66	23.3	10-40 class 2 according to NF EN 14023
										16.5	
										20.9	
										21.8	
										24.1	
21.32											
2	91.46	377.89	286.43	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	5.72	2	14.32	5	62	21.1	25-55 class 3 according to NF EN 14023
										18.6	
										21.6	
										25.1	
										37.6	
24.8											
3	78.09	356.51	278.42	40/50 (TBA=50 Pn=44)	13.921	5	5.56	2	70	16.7	10-40 class 2 according to NF EN 14023
										2	
										7.5	
										2.1	
										6.4	
6.94											

Formulas 1 and 3 are class 2 (10/40) and are therefore rejected. Formula 2 is the only one in class 3 (TBA = 62°C) with an improvement of 7°C, so it will be retained and finally the formula that meets the specifications is as follows:

Pure bitumen 40/50 (TBA=55°C) + 2% ZQ1 + 5% PR FLEX 20 gives "class 3" 25/55 (TBA=62°C).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study offer a judicious combination of the two additives, with specific percentages of 2% for the ZQ1 additive and 5% for the PR FLEX 20 additive, which is identified as being effective in preventing both premature cracking and rutting in pavements. The results obtained demonstrated that this combination achieves an optimum balance between the stiffness and flexibility of BBME, thus reducing the risk of cracking and rutting.

The ZQ1 additive, when used alone, can make BBME stiffer, making it more susceptible to cracking under loads and stresses. On the other hand, the additive PRFLEX 20, when used alone, can increase the flexibility of BBME, which can promote permanent deformation and rutting under the effect of traffic loads.

However, by combining the two additives in the specific proportions mentioned, the mechanical properties of BBME can be optimized. The ZQ1 additive enhances BBME's strength, while the PRFLEX 20 additive improves its flexibility. This combination effectively prevents premature cracking, while reducing the risk of rutting.

It should be stressed that the specific percentages of 2% for ZQ1 and 5% for PRFLEX 20 mentioned are based on the results of this study. These percentages may vary according to project specifications, environmental conditions and the characteristics of the BBME used. It is therefore essential to carry out specific tests and adjustments for each project to determine the optimum proportions to achieve the desired performance.

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